

PROBABILISTIC MULTISCALE METHOD CONSIDERING MULTIPLE RANDOM PARAMETERS IN CONSTITUTIVE MODELS OF MATERIAL PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

In the numerical prediction of the homogenized macroscopic properties of arbitrary heterogeneous material with periodic microstructure, a general formulation of the first-order perturbation based stochastic homogenization(FPSH) method was presented in a discretized form by finite element method in order to consider multiple random parameters of the mechanical properties in the constitutive models. Many random parameters were defined for each material model and for each component of the stress-strain matrix of the constituent's material model.

In order to demonstrative the effectiveness of above formulation, the numerical predictions of 3D printed cellular structure is implemented. Firstly, the variation in the mechanical properties is quantified in 3D printed cellular structure by considering statistical nature of the defects. After manufacturing, the Computed Tomography (CT) technology was used to observe the microstructure in order to evaluate the performance of printed structure. In the raw material, the defects were characterized and categorized into three main groups, i.e. notch, kink and hole. The mechanical properties differ portion by portion due to above defects. Therefore, the FPSH method was utilized to predict the expected and variance of homogenized elastic properties. This study can contribute to improve the manufacturing accuracy in other 3D printed structure by employing the statistical data of defects. Moreover, the micro stress was discussed at the end to get a better solution of both macroscopic stiffness and strength of cellular structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

A two-scale homogenization method that uses an asymptotic expansion of physical quantities has been studied and employed in industries to predict macroscopic mechanical properties. For instance, the formulation for a large deformation problem[1] has been applied to deep-draw forming simulation of fiber reinforced thermoplastics with experimental validation[2]. The defects such as the imperfect adhesion or crack have been considered. However, the analyses were carried out in a deterministic way. If they are used in the Monte Carlo simulation, stochastic prediction is useful[3]. Whereas if reliable results are desired from Monte Carlo simulation with such many random parameters, 10,000 sampling points are usually analyzed, which is very costly.

On the other hand, by means of stochastic finite element method, the deterministic homogenization method has been extended to a new stochastic homogenization method for uncertainty quantification. A spectral stochastic finite element[4], polynomial chaos based stochastic finite element method[5-6], optimal linear expansion scheme[7], second order probabilistic collocation method, the use of maximum entropy principle have been reported. In addition, there are many studies on the stochastic perturbation techniques. Kaminski et al. presented nth-order perturbation method for a simple 1D problem using one random parameter, and then 10th-order perturbation method[8]. On the other hand, the usefulness and reliability of first-order perturbation method have been reported by many researchers[9]. In the above stochastic finite element method and homogenization method, the variability and uncertainty are considered in the physical parameters of composite materials, in other words, in the constituents' mechanical properties.

And in front of the computer simulation design, the defects in law of statistics in view of the manufacturing process, is the important way to understand the defects influence on the structure performance, establish evaluation standards for products indispensable steps. All kinds of simulation

modeling method based on the statistics and analysis technology is important in the study of computer aided engineering statistical simulation tool. These methods to study the structure of composite material can be associated with its performance parameters, can be quantitatively analyzed factors that affect its related properties [9, 10], is of great significance to the composites improve the performance reliability of [11].

In this paper, a general formulation of the first-order perturbation based stochastic homogenization (FPSH) method is presented using arbitrary number of random physical parameters. The presented formulation is easily implemented in a computer code. The characteristic displacement, which appears in the conventional two-scale homogenization method, is theoretically discussed and utilized numerically for verification.

2 GENERAL FORMULATIONS OF PROBABILISTIC MULTISCALE METHOD CONSIDERING RANDOM PARAMETERS IN CONSTITUTIVE MODELS

Suppose a heterogeneous material that has periodic microstructure, whose mechanical properties of constituent materials have variability or uncertainty. Let NMAT be a number of material models of the constituents. Here, each material model has different mechanical properties or different variability. Hence, even for a porous material consisting of one constituent material, if the mechanical properties differ portion by portion in, for instance, 3D printed cellular structure, multiple material models are considered. Arbitrary material model such as anisotropic material is accepted.

Define a stress-strain matrix of a material model i as $[D(\alpha_i)]$, where α is a set of random parameters to describe the variability or uncertainty. Also define $[P_{mn}]$ as Eq.(1), then $[D(\alpha_i)]$ can be expressed by Eq.(2), where $D_{i,mn}$ denotes a component mn in the matrix $[D(\alpha_i)]$.

$$[P_{mn}]_{ij} \equiv \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } (i, j) = (m, n), (n, m) \\ 0 & \text{for others} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$[D(\alpha)_i] = \sum_{m=1}^6 \sum_{n=1}^6 [P_{mn}] D_{i,mn} \quad (2)$$

A random parameter $\alpha_{i,mn}$ is defined for each component of the stress-strain matrix. The expected value of each component is defined as Eq.(3).

$$\text{Exp}\{D_{i,mn}(\alpha_{i,mn})\} = D_{i,mn}^0 \quad (3)$$

Its variance is defined as in Eq.(4), where $f(\bullet)$ denotes the probability density function.

$$\text{Var}\{D_{i,mn}(\alpha_{i,mn})\} = (D_{i,mn}^0)^2 \text{Var}\{f(\alpha_{i,mn})\} \quad (4)$$

Assume that $f(\alpha_{i,mn})$ follows normal distribution with $\text{Exp}[f(\alpha_{i,mn})] = 0$, and $\alpha_{i,mn}$ is small enough. Then, using the approximation based on the first-order perturbation w.r.t. $\alpha_{i,mn}$, the following notation is defined in this paper to describe the variability.

$$D_{i,mn}(\alpha_{i,mn}) \approx D_{i,mn}^0 + D_{i,mn}^0 f(\alpha_{i,mn}) \quad (5)$$

Note now that the major and minor symmetry must hold for $[D(\alpha_i)]$, and therefore

$$f(\alpha_{i,mn}) = f(\alpha_{i,nm}).$$

Due to the microscopic heterogeneity, together with a macroscopic scale x_i , a microscopic scale $y_i = x_i/\lambda$, is defined, where λ denotes a scale ratio between 2 scales. The displacement is expanded asymptotically using λ as follows.

$$u_i^\lambda = u_i^\lambda(x) + \lambda u_i^\lambda(x, y) \quad (6)$$

The superscript means that the physical quantity is dependent on the microstructure. Equation (6) is substituted into a principle of virtual work, Eq.(7), where t_i is a traction.

$$\int_{\Omega} D(\boldsymbol{\alpha})_{ijkl}^{\lambda} \frac{\partial u_k^{\lambda}}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial \delta u_i}{\partial x_j} d\Omega = \int_{\Gamma} t_i \delta u_i d\Gamma \quad (7)$$

An averaging principle for a periodic function g in a microscopic RVE(representative volume element) model Y as shown in Eq.(8)is utilized in the derivation of 2-scale homogenization theory.

$$\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} \int_{\Omega} g\left(\frac{\mathbf{x}}{\lambda}\right) d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y g(\mathbf{y}) dY d\Omega \quad (8)$$

For the elasticity tensor with variability or uncertainty, Eq.(9)is assumed

$$\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0} D(\boldsymbol{\alpha})_{ijkl}^{\lambda} = D(\boldsymbol{\alpha})_{ijkl} \quad (9)$$

In order to split into micro- and macroscopic problems, a characteristic displacement χ_i^{kl} is introduced in the same way with the conventional(deterministic) homogenization theory[19,20].

$$u_i^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = -\chi_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}) \frac{\partial u_k^0(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_l} \quad (10)$$

To this end, a microscopic equation to be solved in RVE is derived as in Eq.(11), and the homogenized macroscopic elasticity tensor can be obtained as in Eq.(12).

$$\int_Y \left(D(\boldsymbol{\alpha})_{ijkl} - D(\boldsymbol{\alpha})_{ijpq} \frac{\partial \chi_p^{kl}}{\partial y_q} \right) \frac{\partial \delta u_i}{\partial y_j} dY = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$D^H(\boldsymbol{\alpha})_{ijkl} = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y \left(D(\boldsymbol{\alpha})_{ijkl} - D(\boldsymbol{\alpha})_{ijpq} \frac{\partial \chi_p^{kl}}{\partial y_q} \right) dY \quad (12)$$

Since the characteristic displacement is also a function of random parameter set $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, it can be expanded based on the first-order perturbation[35-37,39]. However, when many random parameters are defined in this paper, the first-order term must be defined for each material model and for each component of its stress-strain matrix as follows.

$$\{\chi(\boldsymbol{\alpha})\}_{ijkl} = \{\chi^0\}^{kl} + \sum_{i=1}^{NMAT} \sum_{m=1}^6 \sum_{n=m}^6 \{\chi_{i,mn}^1\}^{kl} f(\alpha_{i,mn}) \quad (13)$$

To write the following equations simply, an operator $\{Q^{kl}\}$ is defined, which extracts kl column from a matrix, as in Eq.(15).

$$\{Q^{kl}\} = \{q^{11} \ q^{22} \ q^{33} \ q^{23} \ q^{31} \ q^{12}\}^T \quad (14)$$

$$q^{ij} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } ij = kl \\ 0 & \text{for others} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

Then, the zeroth order term can be calculated by finite element method in the same way with the deterministic homogenization theory by solving Eq.(16).

$$\{\chi^0\}^{kl} = \left(\int_Y [\mathbf{B}]^T [\mathbf{D}]^0 [\mathbf{B}] dY \right)^{-1} \int_Y [\mathbf{B}]^T ([\mathbf{D}]^0 \{Q^{kl}\}) dY \quad (16)$$

Subsequently, the first-order terms can be obtained by solving Eq.(17).

$$\begin{aligned} \{\chi_{i,mn}^1\}^{kl} &= \left(\int_Y [\mathbf{B}]^T [\mathbf{D}]^0 [\mathbf{B}] dY \right)^{-1} \\ &\left\{ \int_Y [\mathbf{B}_i]^T ([\mathbf{P}_{mn}] \{ \mathbf{Q}^{kl} \}) D_{i,mn}^0 dY - \left(\int_Y [\mathbf{B}_i]^T ([\mathbf{P}_{mn}] [\mathbf{B}_i]) D_{i,mn}^0 dY \right) \{ \chi^0 \}^{kl} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Let $\{\chi^0\}$, $\{\chi_i^{kl}\}^1$ be a collection of zeroth and first-order terms of the characteristic displacements. Then, the zeroth and first-order terms of the homogenized macroscopic stress-strain matrices are obtained by Eqs.(18-19). $[\mathbf{I}]$ is an identity matrix.

$$[\mathbf{D}^H]^0 = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y [\mathbf{D}]^0 ([\mathbf{I}] - [\mathbf{B}][\chi]^0) dY \quad (18)$$

$$[\mathbf{D}_{i,mn}^H]^1 = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y [\mathbf{P}_{mn}]^0 ([\mathbf{I}] - [\mathbf{B}][\chi]^0) D_{i,mn}^0 dY - \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y [\mathbf{D}]^0 [\mathbf{B}] [\chi_{i,mn}]^1 dY \quad (19)$$

Using them, the homogenized macroscopic stress-strain matrix can be finally calculated as Eq.(20).

$$[\mathbf{D}^H(\alpha)] = [\mathbf{D}^H]^0 + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{MAT}} \sum_{m=1}^6 \sum_{n=m}^6 [\mathbf{D}_{i,mn}^H]^1 f(\alpha_{i,mn}) \quad (20)$$

It allows us to write the global behavior of the heterogeneous material in a conventional way as shown in Eq.(21)

$$\left(\int_{\Omega} [\mathbf{B}]^T [\mathbf{D}^H(\alpha)] [\mathbf{B}] d\Omega \right) \{u\}^0 = \int_{\Gamma} [\mathbf{N}]^T \{t\} d\Gamma \quad (21)$$

3 NUMERICAL DEMONSTRATIVE EXAMPLE OF 3D PRINTING CELLULAR STRUCTURE

In order to verify the formulation in the section 2, a numerical example was applied. The code was developed and implemented successfully. And the numerical process is followed in this section.

3.1 Reconstruction and statistical data of imperfections in 3D printed cellular structure

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of reconstruction and imperfect observation from 3D printed cellular structure. (a) CAD model design of 3D printing; (b) 2D scanned images and segmentation process; (c) 3D voxel model construction.

A cellular structure analysed in this study is from a 3D printed cubic lattice unit cells in Fig. 1(a). The strut has thickness $t=1\text{mm}$, and cubic lattice unit cell has length $d=4\text{mm}$. The complete cellular structure has $n=5$ cells in each direction, which gives overall dimensions of $26 \times 26 \times 26 \text{mm}^3$. The model is manufactured by a selective laser sintering EOS M 280, which has a maximum laser output power of 400 W and a scanning speed of 10 mm/s, scanning spacing of 0.04 mm, scanning strategy using the Z axis from negative to positive direction scanning. In order to identify the elastic properties of the specimen and numerical analysis, a 2D scanning was conducted using a computer tomography (CT) scanner at a resolution technology of approximately. The 3D models of the fabricated individual struts

are reconstructed from the 2D scan images using a reconstruction process depicted in Fig. 1(b). The images are then combined and converted to a high-resolution FE mesh with 8 node voxel elements as shown in Fig. 1(c). From Fig. 1(c), the struct imperfections can be obtained to characterize the uncertainties of the volume irregularities.

Figure 2: Two support types along building direction: (a) model I as $B=45^{\circ}$; (b) model II as $B=0^{\circ}$.

Two supporting directions in Fig. 2 are chosen in this study. Fig. 2(a) is supposed to be easier for some struts in horizontal direction than that in Fig. 2(b), since Suard et.al. [11] studied the morphology of printed structure is correlated with the building direction. 45° and 0° of structure axes w.r.t. building directions are typical. It's found in the study that different types of imperfection differ correlated with the supporting type closely in later section. The result such as notch was shown in Fig. 4. The type of notch was only found both in support type A and support B. In support type A, extra type was kink. In support type B, extra type was hole.

Use of randomness in morphology will help the numerical simulation in the 3D printed structures. Therefore, a characterization method for morphological uncertainties are shown as Fig. 3. Figure 3(a) shows a dimension definition of notch; Fig. 3(b) shows another type of imperfection defined as kink. Also in the struts, holes in material are observed as shown in Fig. 3(c).

Select local structure containing imperfection as shown in a local scale down to 1 mm, imperfection center for local coordinate origin, expressed as $x-t_1-t_2$ axis direction. Along the longitudinal x direction (0.5 mm to 0.5 mm), defect feature dimensions were measured. Notch with angle mark n and its feature sizes is shown in Fig. 3(a), contains the position ξ_n , notch length a_n , residual thickness b_n . The feature sizes of kink is shown as Fig. 3(b), which contains the kink position ξ_k , kink angle θ_k , opening length a_k and residual thickness b_k . Hole (hole) is shown as Fig. 3(c), in which its feature sizes contains the location of the hole ξ_H , vertical and horizontal axial length a_H , b_H .

Figure 3: Imperfections characterization of struts: (a) notch; (b) kink; (c) hole.

The results of notch dimensions as defined in Fig. 3(a) were shown in Fig. 4. The normal distribution could be used to fit for the data. The mean value was 0.41 and standard deviation was 0.11. Horizontal model is established based on the statistical rule of, lateral and horizontal direction in 45° placed the stochastic model I and stochastic model II. Stochastic model contains , in the overall number of bar for 540, gap accounted for 2.46914%, warping accounted for 2.5%, accounted for 1.66667% of the hole, (a_n , b_n , a_k , b_k , θ_k , a_H , b_H) adopt normal distribution. To evaluate other 3D printed products, the description of defects' geometric parameters still has reference significance for

other 3D printing defects. The statistical distribution characteristics of other two defects' parameters were shown in Fig.10 and Fig. 11 and listed as table 1 in appendix.

Figure 4: Statistical data of notch dimension: (a) a typical length a_n ; (b) a typical width b_n .

3.3 Probabilistic numerical analysis for homogenized properties based on FPSH method

Following the statistical data build as Fig. 4 and Fig. 9-10 in the appendix, the numerical simulation models were shown in Fig. 5, in which the location of the defects was generated by MATLAB random function rand.

Figure 5: Generated random models with imperfections based on statistical data: (a) random model I; (b) random model II.

The homogenized elastic stiffness for the lattice structure was plotted in Fig. 6 after normalization by that of perfect model. Also, the numerical results by the stochastic prediction were plotted in blue bar and black error bar. The blue bar shows the expected value, and the blue bar shows $\pm 3E^H_{S.D.}$.

The stiffness of random model I and II was largely reduced compared to perfect model. The uncertainty setup in FPSH could consider the possible variability. Since the homogenized density was not so largely scattered, the variability of normalized homogenized elastic stiffness didn't have a big difference.

Figure 6: Comparison on expected value and variance of normalized homogenized elastic stiffness for numerical perfect model, random model I and random model II.

4 DISCUSSION

For initial perfect model and two kinds of random geometry model, micro stress analysis was followed in a one-way tensile simulation as shown in Fig. 7. Uniform pressure was applied with an average 5MPa in X direction. Figure 7 shows tensile stress results. Compared with the Fig. 7(a) initial zero defect model, Fig. 7(b) ~ (c) shows the maximum stress with inclusion of notch, kink and holes. In the stochastic models I and II, stress concentration is obvious to be seen. $\text{Max}(s_x)$ $\text{Max}(s_y)$ $\text{Max}(s_z)$ is the maximum stress.

Figure 8 shows comparison result of three models, with inclusion of the average stress and maximum stress. The results show that the initial model, stochastic model I and II of the average stress is the same, and the average stress is not affected by defects. The maximum stress in the Y direction is the largest in the stochastic model II, followed by stochastic model I and initial zero defect model. Z direction of the maximum stress shows no big difference in the three models. This study stress out concentration caused by the pore diameter of only 0.8 mm. Cunningham [13] choose electron beam melting for Ti6Al4V, no potential risk of crack line appears. This study shows that among laser sintering process, the internal structure of electron beam melting can get more dense optimization.

Figure 7: Mises stress contour plot of perfect model, random model I and random model II.

Figure 8: Comparison between maximum stress and averaged stress of perfect model, random model I and random model II.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a general formulation of the first-order perturbation based stochastic homogenization method for composite materials, porous materials or cellular structures considering many random physical parameters. In the derivation, the features of the characteristic displacement

that is defined in the 2-scale homogenization theory were discussed. 21 independent random parameters for both isotropic and orthotropic material models were considered in the numerical example. It was revealed that the proposed formulation could predict the variability in the homogenized macroscopic properties accurately.

In this paper, we study a kind of technological process of the preparation of porous structure using SLS prototyping, discussed several process parameters on its performance. And by using CT and three-dimensional image reconstruction technique to evaluate the microstructure defects, the defect geometry parameters of statistical data; Was built based on statistics and numerical model with random defects, compared with the initial design without defect structure is analyzed, the performance of the error brought by the random defects, lead to anisotropy of the microscopic stress distribution. It concludes the following conclusion:

(1) a geometric defects such as holes, notch, kink direction and building direction is relevant, connecting cellular structure sample building direction greatly influences the performance of the component mechanical properties, because of inhomogeneity. Sample is placed on the workbench direction and defect formation has a certain relationship. When the sample weight and scanning stack in the same direction, studio gases trapped in the liquid metal layer, forming a pore. When the sample weight and scanning direction, print heads sinter cooling easily when forming warp.

(2) the statistical parameters of interconnected cellular structure defect quantitative analysis, it is found the SLS parts, defect parameters in accordance with normal distribution or lognormal distribution. Due to the total number of samples is big enough, so the statistical regularity of the calibration for the equipment to print out the other structure still apply.

(3) two different directions of stochastic model of macroscopic stiffness and permeability analysis, compared with the initial design without defects, the error is within 5%. Microscopic local stress analysis to get maximum micro stress exists in stochastic model I more than the risk of yield stress, the decrease of strength caused by defects can not be ignored. So in SLS printed structures, it needs to check the strength.

Application of statistical regularity of the above defects random numerical simulation model is set up, this equipment manufacturing parts by the forecasting error, saves the microstructure test cost. SLS prototyping parts reliability assessment has important practical application value.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Takano, N., Ohnishi, Y., Zako, M., Nishiyabu, K.: The formulation of homogenization method applied to large deformation problem for composites materials. *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 37. 6517-6535 (2000).
- [2] Takano, N., Ohnishi, Y., Zako, M., Nishiyabu, K.: Microstructure-based deep-drawing simulation of knitted fabric reinforced thermoplastics by homogenization theory. *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 38. 6333-6356 (2001).
- [3] Guinovart-Diaz, R.M., Rodrigues-Ramos, R., Lopez-Realpozo, J.C., Bravo-Castillero, J., Otero, J.A., Sabina, F.J., Lebon, F., Dumont, S: Analysis of fibrous elastic composites with nonuniform imperfect adhesion. *Acta Mech.* 227. 57-73 (2016).
- [4] Almasi, A., Silani, M., Talebi, H., Rabczuk, T.: Stochastic analysis of the interphase effects on the mechanical properties of clay/epoxy nanocomposites. *Compo. Struct.* 133. 1302-1312 (2015).
- [5] Sepahvand, K: Spectral stochastic finite element vibration analysis of fiber-reinforced composites with random fiber orientation. *Compo. Struct.* 145. 119-128 (2016).

- [6] Sasikumar, P., Suresh, R., Gupta, S.: Stochastic model order reduction in uncertainty quantification of composite structures. *Compo. Struct.* 128. 21-34 (2015).
- [7] Clement, A., Soize, C., Yvonnet, J.: Uncertainty quantification in computational stochastic multiscale analysis fo nonlinear elastic materials. *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.* 254. 61-82 (2013).
- [8] Kaminski, M., Szafran, J.: Perturbation-based stochastic finite element analysis of the interface defects in composites via reponse function method. *Compo. Struct.* 97. 269-276 (2013).
- [9] Talha, M., Singh, B.N.: Stochastic perturbation-based finite element for buckling statistics of FGM plates with uncertain material properties in thermal environments. *Compo. Struct.* 108. 823-833 (2014).
- [10] Qiu, Z., Wang, X., Parameter perturbation method for dynamic responses of structures with uncertain but bounded parameters based on interval analysis, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 42. 4958-4970 (2005).
- [11] WEI Qingsong, TANG Ping, WU Jiamin, ZHOU Jian, Microstructure and mechanical performance of porous cordierite ceramic parts manufactured by selective laser sintering[J], *Journal of huazhong university of science and technology*, 2016,6:46-51.
- [12] Suard M, Martin G, Lhuissier P, Dendievel R, Vignat F, Blandin JJ, Villeneuve F, Mechanical equivalent diameter of single struts for the stiffness prediction of lattice structures produced by electron beam melting. *Additive Manufacturing*, 8, 2015, pp: 124-131.
- [13] R. Cunningham, S. P. Narra, T. Ozturk, J. Beuth, and A. D. Rollett, Evaluating the effect of processing parameters on porosity in electron beam melted Ti-6Al-4V via synchrotron X-ray microtomography, *Journal of the minerals, metals and materials*, 2016,68:765-771.

APPENDIX

Figure 9: Statistical data of kink dimension: (a) a typical length a_k ; (b) a typical width b_k ; (c) a typical width θ_k

Figure 10: Statistical data of notch dimension: (a) a typical length a_H ; (b) a typical width b_H .

Table 1. Statistics of geometric parameters for defects defined in section 2

Defect's geometric parameters	Number of samples	Number of defects	Probabilistic distribution	Mean value (mm)	Standard Variation (mm)	Minimum value(mm)	Maximum value(mm)
a_n	3168 (1008-0° , 2160-45°)	80	Normal distribution	0.41	0.11	0.1	0.625
b_n	3168 (1008-0° , 2160-45°)	80	Normal distribution	0.55	0.17	0.2	0.9
a_k	2160 (45°)	54	Log normal distribution	0.53	0.09	0.375	0.7
b_k	2160 (45°)	54	Log normal distribution	0.38	0.14	0.2	0.7
θ_k	2160 (45°)	54	Log normal distribution	112°	14°	90°	150°
a_H	1080 (0°)	18	Normal distribution	0.34	0.15	0.1	0.55
b_H	1080 (0°)	18	Normal distribution	0.56	0.14	0.3	0.8